

*Smart system of renewable energy storage based on **IN**tegrated **EV**s and **bA**tteries to empower mobile, **D**istributed and centralised **E**nergy storage in the distribution grid*

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Table of contents

Executive summary	7
1 Introduction	8
1.1 Introducing the cases	10
1.1.1 Case 1: Home charging in Norway	10
1.2 Case 2: Public smart charging in the Netherlands	11
2 Theoretical perspectives on end use of electricity and the everyday life revisited	13
2.1 Practice Theory	13
2.2 Domestication theory	14
2.3 Technological script	15
2.4 Socio-technical imaginaries	15
2.5 Summary of theoretical perspectives	16
3 Research methods	17
3.1 Gender and recruitment	18
3.2 Analysis of end user data	18
3.3 The informants	19
4 Technology domestication and end user experience	21
4.1 Charging routines in everyday life	21
4.1.1 The socio-technical habits of EV driving	23
4.1.2 Family life and resource competence	24
4.1.3 End user understanding of the flexibility of the grid	27
4.1.4 The economic rationale of the end user	29
4.2 Expert perspectives on EV end use and smart charging	30
4.2.1 Make it simple!	31

4.2.2	The feeling of control	33
4.2.3	What happens when smart charging is backgrounded?	34
4.2.4	Ways of thinking about flexibility	37
5	Discussion	41
5.1	Socio-technical imaginaries and the affordance of end users	41
5.2	The context of flexible end use	44
6	Conclusions	48
7	References	50
7.1	References for consideration	52
8	Appendix	54
8.1	Appendix 1: Interview guide Norwegian case	54
8.2	Appendix 2: Interview guide for INVADE D9.2. Expert users the Netherlands case.	58

Abbreviations and Acronyms

Acronym	Description
DSM	Demand-Side Management
DR	Demand Response
EV	Electric Vehicle
PV	Photovoltaic
ICEV	Internal Combustion Engine Vehicle
DIY	Do it yourself
BRP	Balance Responsible Party
DSO	Distribution System Operator
ESCO	Energy Service Company

Executive summary

The initial purpose of this report was to explore user experience with and behavior effects of the INVADE platform. However, because the INVADE platform was not implemented in pilot settings in time for the study, user experiences with the INVADE platform have not been available for examination. Thus, this report is focused on the data that was available, namely smart charging use cases in Norway and the Netherlands, more specifically use case 1. The report gives detailed insight on the charging habits of the end users and the potential for flexibility.

The empirical data in this report has been collected by qualitative investigations of technology end use in everyday life, experiences of end users with EVs and smart charging, interviews with end users in the Norwegian Lyse Pilot and expert developers in a pilot undertaken by Elaad/GreenFlux. The report highlights how new technology, in this case smart EV charging, steadily becomes an integrated part of the end user's everyday routine, through an adoption process analysed as a process of technology domestication.

This report consists of five parts. Part one is an introduction to UC1 in Norway and the Netherlands. Part two revisits the theoretical framework established in D9.2 *Input on user behaviour and technology domestication*. Part three describes the methodology. Part four presents the empirical analysis of the findings. Part five presents an inductive framework based on the empirical analysis that produces different but distinct variations of end user types according to how they relate to and adapt technology deployed within the INVADE use cases. The main finding of this report is that the INVADE pilots provide a variety of contexts in which end users can acquire knowledge about the grid and grid-related technologies. End user learning about INVADE technology was moderated by specific constraints related to infrastructure, culture and practice, and that also varies across different national contexts. For instance, the report finds that different ways of organizing housing, living and parking (renting vs. owning a dwelling, public vs. private parking, etc.) in Norway and the Netherlands have a strong bearing on how end users (and grid operators) adapt charging technology.

The conclusion of this report indicates a saturation point has been achieved in terms of providing insight about end user behaviour and adaption of (semi-)smart charging technology. Further studies should be conducted for a comprehensive understanding of V2G, user interaction with the INVADE flexibility platform, and use of batteries.

1 Introduction

The EU has committed to reducing greenhouse gas emissions. One central way of achieving this is by introducing more renewable energy in form of wind and solar power, combined with an electrification of the transport sector. This transition will challenge the way the power grid is currently operated, since these new sources of electricity are more intermittent and harder to predict. Changes further challenging the grid is the increased electricity consumption, demanding further investment in grid capacity. Tackling these challenges in the most effective way is not possible without introducing new tools based on Information and Communication Technology (ICT), that can measure, identify and leverage increased amounts of flexibility in the grid.

The INVADE project has explored and developed solutions to harness flexibility potential at the site of the end user and leverage this flexibility for balancing purposes in the grid, thereby making it more feasible to steadily increase the share of renewables in the power mix. Flexibility is primarily “harvested” at consumer level, where it can be gained from shifting end use of electricity to times when demand is lower. Flexible electricity can also be generated locally, for instance by PV, and then stored, used for local consumption, or provided to a flexibility market. Buyers of flexibility will aggregate and market it to Distribution System Operators (DSO) and Balancing Responsible Parties (BRP), making a profit for themselves and the energy system (and society) by negating grid investment needs. Additionally, providers of flexibility may save or profit by shifting their scheduled use or generating locally for self-consumption as a prosumer. In the INVADE project, flexibility is aggregated and provided by the INVADE platform, which can control and optimize consumption patterns according to user need, market signals and system constraints.

In order to demonstrate the feasibility of this, this report was intended to report from a qualitative study of end use experiences with the INVADE platform. However, at the time of the study, which was implemented late in the project in order to secure maturity of pilot subjects, the INVADE platform was not functionally implemented in any pilots available for study. This has had the unfortunate consequence that data on experience with the INVADE platform has not been available to study in time for the project deadline. To mitigate this, the report instead focuses on end users of Electric Vehicles (EVs) and

charging practices in Norway and the Netherlands. Based on interview data with users and developers, it evaluates flexibility potential at the site of electricity consumers. This provides detailed insight about the kind of framework within which the INVADE platform may be implemented. It also examines and compares two slightly different frameworks, namely the Norwegian and the Dutch.

In the future, end users will be the suppliers of potential flexibility by shifting their electricity demand. Thus, supply of flexibility correlates directly with the willingness, ability and capability of end users to deliver it. Thus, the framework that is provided for any flexibility operator is shaped by culture, knowledge and individual attitudes¹. The EV transition is increasing the load on local grids and transformer stations and increasing shares of renewables is making it harder for Energy Service Companies (ESCO) to predict load profiles. This is steadily increasing the need for BRP and DSOs to manage the challenge of low capacity or imbalances, especially in areas where EV penetration is high. One way of doing this is by introducing systems at the household and building level for flexible end use of electricity that is consumed by EV charging.

The EV transition in Norway and the Netherlands provide a strong case for giving insight on how users think about and define their potential flexibility, and what they consider the appropriate conditions for relinquishing it. This report compares a Norwegian case with smart EV charging in the Netherlands, where much of the flexibility operation is invisible and backgrounded, to the point where most EV owners are in fact unable to easily separate it from conventional charging, and unable to know the rate at which the car is charging. This deals with a common question related to concepts of smart energy use and end use flexibility potential: to what extent should users be expected to make an effort to generate flexibility, as opposed to what extent flexibility aggregation can simply happen in the background, with the lowest impact on comfort and convenience of everyday life?

¹ https://echoes-project.eu/sites/echoes.drupal.pulsartecnalia.com/files/ECHOES_D5.3_Enabling%20factors%20for%20collective%20consumer%20action.pdf

This report presents the empirical findings on the end users' domestication of Electric Vehicles (EV) and home charging in the Norwegian Lyse pilot study in Stavanger and ELaad's public EV charging in the Netherlands. The focus of the report is end users of EVs and their charging habits in their everyday life. The report provides insight into end user attitudes regarding the potential in the INVADE platform for user flexibility and smart charging. Based on an analysis of empirical data from qualitative interviews with end users and households that participate in the INVADE pilots, as well as experts behind the development, the findings in this report provides valuable insight for implementing flexibility platforms and related technologies in the future.

1.1 Introducing the cases

The Norwegian case and the Dutch case represent two different ways of implementing the INVADE platform. This report ultimately deals with the question of user involvement and how to consider end users when implementing flexibility operations. End users have different knowledge of technology, different technological interest, varying degree of competences and lifestyles, as well as different material surroundings, all of which influence the way technologies are used in practice.

1.1.1 Case 1: Home charging in Norway

In Norway, the rate of home ownership is high, as about $\frac{3}{4}$ of the households in Norway are owned. The most common type of home is the single unit dwelling, followed by semi-detached houses, row houses and apartment flats (Revold et al., 2018). The combination of such a dwelling structure with strict parking regulations has resulted in that fact that many people in Norway also own their parking lot. This leads to expectations in the population of having the ability to charge their EVs at home.

In the Norwegian Lyse demonstration project in Stavanger, smart charging capability is installed at 18 customers. Recruitment for the demonstration project took place by email, where a number of Lyse's customers were offered a home EV charger installed for half the price of a normal retail price charger on a first-come-first-serve basis. This was arguably perceived as a good deal by many: After only 30 minutes, the offer was fully booked. The offer came with installation included, and the charger was delivered and installed at the premises of the customer. The charger was typically put inside a private

garage, or on a fence or wall next to a parking space. In most cases, the installer would also add a dedicated circuit for the charger.

Figure 1: Smart charger placement

The smartness of these chargers lies in their ability to deploy the INVADE platform at the site of the consumer, thus providing charging that can be subjected to Demand Response (DR) and Demand Side Management (DSM). This means that the charge load can be shifted to times of less demand and when prices are lower, consequently benefiting both the grid and the customer. At the time of the study, however, the smartness of these chargers had yet to be introduced, and they were operated as a conventional charger supplying the car with power once it was plugged in (unless a different charging schedule was designated by manual input to the car). Customers were still very happy with their charger, however, and reported to be happy with the installation of a reduced priced charger that provided them with a convenient supply of electricity at their home and added fire safety.

1.2 Case 2: Public smart charging in the Netherlands

In the Netherlands, it is estimated that 60 percent of households own their house. About 43 % own a car and 5 % have access to a company car (Statistics Netherlands, 2019). Most of the car owners in the Netherlands park their car in public facilities or in the streets outside of where they live.

In the Netherlands, the case studied for this report was a smart charging pilot project focused on a simulated neighborhood charging plot. In this case the users were for the most part unaware of their participation in a smart charging project, thus the findings from this case study is based on interviews with INVADE technology developers from ElaadNL and GreenFlux. The Elaad pilot was of a different configuration and a larger scale than the Norwegian one. The pilot was testing smart charging for around 1000 public chargers spread around the Netherlands but simulated to be gathered in two neighborhood areas. Acting on a simulated signal from the DSO indicating the maximum grid capacity in these neighborhoods, a curtailment algorithm was in place to regulate charging to accommodate this limit across all chargers. Thus, the locations of the chargers were fictional, but the charging and curtailment procedures were not.

2 Theoretical perspectives on end use of electricity and the everyday life revisited

In deliverable D9.2 Input on user behavior and technology domestication amongst users to the business model development (Thronsen and Ryghaug 2018), four theoretical concepts were introduced that provide insight into how users interact with new knowledge and technology, taking into consideration the existing, everyday life setting. These four theoretical concepts were 1) **practice theory**, which understands technology interventions as parts of already existing and slowly changing energy cultures, where technology must become part of practices that make up everyday life in order to be useful, 2) **domestication theory** which is concerned with practical, cognitive, and symbolic aspects of technology appropriation processes, useful for evaluation of users' motivation for appropriation, learning and know-how, and concerns of self-representation when technology is appropriated and put into use, 3) the concept of **technological scripts** written into technology and consequently read and interpreted by users, linking design processes and end use, and finally 4) **socio-technical imaginaries** that explore development and implementation of technologies via the concept of imagined use and imagined users in the design process. The four approaches are summarized in the following.

2.1 Practice Theory

Practice theory mainly considers consumption a consequence and not a cause and focuses on individual competency but also to a large degree on physical objects (Shove & Walker 2014, also see Warde 2005, Shove 2003, Schatzki 2010). Practices are considered as the “site” of the social, or nexuses of saying and doing, and that the act of saying and doing within these nexuses reproduce, transform, and perpetuate the practices carried within them. It approaches from the point of view of the many practices, for instance, in a household. In terms of WP9 goals, practice theory can be used to understand how practices within households can and must change to fulfil end users' specific roles in participating in a pilot, and that participating in the pilot is not itself the cause of change.

Electric mobility and electricity use in general takes place within energy cultures comprised of a wider suite of practices that define everyday life. Everyday life is made

up of tasks, many of which do not necessarily involve evaluating energy consumption even though they may relate to energy consumption indirectly. Such tasks are aimed at mobility, cooking, cleanliness, cosiness and other routines of the mundane. For end users, evaluating electricity consumption vis-à-vis undertaking such tasks is secondary, as the tasks exist simply according to their own necessity. This is what makes people consider their own electricity use as inflexible and why pay their bill as a matter of course. Practices are what defines the way any task or activity gets done. Practices are often embodied, meaning we don't actively employ cognitive skills to do them: we just do them. As such, practices are often routinized.

The consequence of this is that electricity use is invisible to users. The practices that take place within the home have arisen partially because of and in parallel with other, tightly interwoven practices of everyday life. To more fully understand what electricity consumption is about, we can explore ongoing practices that cause electricity to be consumed.

2.2 Domestication theory

Domestication theory is a way of analyzing technology appropriation processes by paying attention to 1) practical, 2) cognitive, and 3) symbolic aspects (see Silverstone et al. 1992, Berker et al. 2006, Sørensen 2006, 2013). In short, evaluating 1) practical aspects, determine what a new technological artefact or a novel piece of knowledge can be used for, if and when we are allowed to use it, or the appropriate way of using. Then there are 2) cognitive aspects, governed by if we know how to use it, understand what it is for, or if and how we can learn or be taught by someone how to use it. Finally, the 3) symbolic aspect determines among other things identity markers, or the ways in which technological artefacts can be used to signify to others one's values and concerns.

This grants us the perspective that technology use has attached to it values and meanings, which may or may not be visible and interpretable to others. This last point is crucial with respect to creating the right kinds of incentives for participation in INVADE pilots by end users when monetary incentives cannot be relied upon alone. As the symbolic aspect underlines, technologies enter into social life and become part of our relationships with other people, including issues of rule setting and guideline provision.

This means that for an end user, value and meaning is assigned to for instance an electric vehicle or a solar panel rooftop rig visible to for instance the neighbors.

2.3 Technological script

When studying end users and technology within science and technology, a common point of entry is by looking at how things are designed, as it is considered to influence how things end up being used. For this a framework has been adopted, that simply put analyses technology as if it were text. But where can we find the meaning of a text? Is it within the text itself, or is it produced as it is read? Within the field of hermeneutics, the most common answer to the question of meaning is that it arises as a synthesis of the reader's preconditions and the intended message of the text. When analysing the intersection of technological artefacts and human beings, the same question regarding meaningful use of technology can be posed. This has led to what is known as script theory (Akrich 1992, Akrich & Latour 1992).

In short, we can say that designers shape technology in such a manner that instructions for proper use is embedded within the design. This is often what is referred to as “good design”, or what one with design parlance might refer to as a high degree of affordance. The thing presents itself in a way that more or less immediately reveals to the user how it is meant to be used, what it is for, and the role of the user in relation to it. The script is a program for action, the program the user relates to when engaging with machine or artefact. When the artefact leaves the hands of the designer and is placed in the hands of users, they have some freedom over whether to follow the script, change it, or even oppose it altogether. These are cases then, in which the user employs anti-programs. The relevance for WP9 is evident in the following example, which also sheds some light on how domestication and practice theory features in everyday life.

2.4 Socio-technical imaginaries

A consequence of considering technology as scripted devices is that users may have influence over objects beyond the intentions of designers, whose responsibilities are often limited to designing for ideal scenarios. This active role of users in meeting technology evidences that they are not simply passive or rational. Often there are conditions outside the realm of user and designer both that explain the success, or lack thereof, of an artefact in doing what it was supposed to. Still, shaping technology is about making choices on behalf of the user in advance of the use situation. The concept of

socio-technical imaginaries (Jasanoff and Kim 2009), as well as what has been described as imagined lay persons (ILP) (Maranta et al., 2003), can be considered that which influences assumption made on behalf of users by designers of technology and policy alike.

2.5 Summary of theoretical perspectives

Though admitting the role of imaginaries in influencing technology innovation and development processes, the necessity of imaginaries for such processes to achieve momentum at all cannot be underestimated. Technology development is about making choices on behalf of users and of the future of society. Woolgar (1991) has described the designer as someone who “configure the user”, whereby a frame is created around the technology for correct use. With this in mind, it is possible to say that technology itself can have a normative capacity. If technology does have normative capacity, it means that it can implement guidelines, for instance, for how electricity should and should not be used.

Electric mobility and smart charging are normative. The basis of the norms carried by technology (for instance the imperative to reduce peak consumption) has its origin in energy policy. Smart energy technology can be a way of configuring users according to greater principles of energy markets and policy. But for norms to have any kind of ordering force they must resonate with people. So then must technology, if it is to carry norms.

3 Research methods

In this part of the study a qualitative research method was found most appropriate, as the goal was to interpret and understand how end users interact with and experience the technology of smart charging. A semi-structured interview method was used. This method follows a set of pre-determined topics and questions, that allows for the interviewer to let the informant pursue the topics that they find most interesting and relevant (Kvale, 1997). The interviews have been transcribed verbatim, and the text analyzed in the tradition of qualitative research methods. The conversations have provided individual experiences and understandings technologies used in the INVADE pilots, such as smart charging technologies, EV related practices, electricity consumption habits, as well as experiences with the INVADE project.

The pilots provide both a demonstration and a learning opportunity for the companies that develop the pilots, but also for the end user in their private home. In the case of public charging in the Netherlands, because of the nature of the pilots described in the above, the pilot did not require and could not provide us with any active or engaged end users. Thus, in this case we relied on expert interviews, rather than end users. In case of the expert interview data, the focus was on the way end users are envisioned by the designers of the technology, the framework in which the technology is deployed, including what experience experts have with end users. By analyzing both user data and expert data it is possible to compare experiences and technological implications in the case of active, engaged users (Norway) and expert views of users as unknowing of smart solutions that “just work” (Netherlands).

In the Norwegian case we used contact information provided by Lyse for 18 end users of Lyse chargers that were considered to be “smart capable”, but still not connected to the INVADE platform due to technical issues. Out of the population of 18 end users that we were given access to, 14 responded. In the Dutch pilot, the pilot on smart charging dealt with public chargers that were not directly connected to private homes. Thus, the informants for this part of the report consisted of 8 experts working in Elaad and GreenFlux with developing and implementing smart charging in the Netherlands, in addition to three expert interviews from the Norwegian case. Interviews lasted on average about 1 to 1.5 hours and were in the Norwegian case conducted in the pilot

users' homes. The interviews with the experts in Netherland were conducted at the offices of ElaadNL and over Skype and lasted about 1 hour (see appendix 1-2 for interview guides).

3.1 Gender and recruitment

Most of the respondents were men. Of the interviewees, 1 out of 11 of the experts were female, 3 out of 14 end users interview objects were female. Of all the signatories for participation in the Norwegian pilot with smart charging, two were women. This means that since a man was the signatory of the pilot participation contract, this was the reason mostly men have been contacted for interviews. In three of the interviews, a woman participated more or less in the interview (once as a full participant, otherwise participating more or less in the background, providing short remarks or comments). In many cases women and grown children were users of EVs and chargers but did not participate in the interview.

3.2 Analysis of end user data

All end-user interviews were recorded and transcribed. Transcribed material was coded with detailed “empirical-close coding” in HyperRESEARCH, a qualitative analysis software program. Following Tjora (2017), this way of coding ensures that the coded material retains a closeness to the empirical data. A total of 442 codes were generated and assigned titles like *“Those who live far away charge at the workplace”*, *“can set car to charge at a given time”* and *“If we had lost power at peak hours then I think more would have been aware of the electricity grid”*. After coding the data, codes were grouped according to interrelation. This left us with 27 different code groups that represented the motivation of the end-users, barriers to EV charging, and user flexibility in everyday life. This code group was then sorted into six main categories, each comprising a sublevel of findings. The six main categories are:

- The rationale for choosing electric mobility
- Charging routines and the everyday life
- Socio-technical habits of EV driving
- Technological playfulness
- Economic rationale
- Understanding the electricity grid

These six categories of end users made up the empirical foundation for the analysis of domestication of EVs and charging practices.

In the case of the Dutch pilot, we conducted 8 expert interviews. In conjunction with the Norwegian pilot we also interviewed three experts and included them in the expert analysis part of the report. The interviews were once again coded based on a closeness to the empirical data, and categories were discovered that represented a range of issues and concerns experts have about both the state of the grid, EV use, smart charging, and their observations on user preferences and experiences.

3.3 The informants

Table 1: The informants and some general information about their cars and driving and charging practices

	No. of cars	Car no. 1	Type	Yearly milage (km)	Charger no. 1	Charging	Daily use (hrs)	Why INVADE?
1	2	EV	BMW i3	EV: 8000 D: 6000	Home	Afternoon	1	Charger deal
2	2	EV	BMW225xe BMW i3	H: 12000 km EV: 8000	Home	Afternoon	1	Charger deal
3	1	EV	BMW i3	EV: 6000	Home	Midnight, By app	1	Charger deal, tech interest
4	1	Hybrid	Audi-e-Tron	EV: 6000	Home	On park	>1	Charger deal
5	2	Hybrid	Mercedes	H: 6000 H: Work car	Home	Afternoon	>1	Charger deal
6	2	Ionic	Ionic, Touran	EV: 1000	Home	Afternoon	>1	Charger deal
7	2	eGolf	Tesla eGolf (work car)	EV: 12 000 EV: 30 000	70 % home 30 % work.	Tesla: 2x week, eGolf: work or home	4	Charger deal
8	3	Diesel	2 IONIQ 1 Diesel van	EV: 1500 D: 2000	Home	On park	1	Tech interest, PV pilot
9	2	EV	BMW i3 Volvo	EV: 10 000	Home	Midnight	1	Fire safe, tech interest
10	2	EV	E-Golf, Mercedes R350 CDI	EV: 12 000 D: 10 000	Home	Midnight, By app	2	Fire safe, tech interest
11	1	EV	BMW i3	EV: 10 000	Home	On park	1	Fire safe, fast charge
12	1	Hybrid	Ioniq	H: 12 000	—	—	—	Charger deal
13	2	EV	Leaf, Mondeo	EV: 18 000 D: 8000	Home	Midnight, Manual input	1	Charger deal, fire safe, tech interest
14	2	EV	BMW i3, Mercedes	EV: 20 000 D: 17 000	Home	Evening	3	Charger deal, tech interest
15	2	EV	Hyundai Kona Volvo XC60	EV: 25 000 D: 12 000	At work, Home	Midnight, Manual input	2	Charger deal, project interest

The Lyse demonstration in Stavanger had 18 pilot users that have installed a smart capable charging unit on their premises, 14 of which were interviewed. Three of them were also able to provide answers to some follow-up questions by email. A detailed overview of the end users across parameters such as EV type, driving and charging habits, and motivation for participating is summarized in table 1. An overview of the expert informants can be found in tables 2 and 3.

Table 2: Experts informants from the Dutch pilot setting GreenFlux/ElaadNL

	Name	Role	Affiliation
1	Fedja Zdrnja	Developer	ElaadNL
2	Stan Janssen	Project manager	ElaadNL
3	Arjan Wargers	R&I manager	Enexis
4	Marisca Zweistra	Project manager	ElaadNL
5	Stefan van den Boos*	Technical project manager/EV Driver	Eneco
6	Jefta van Hees	Pilot owner, HOME & OFFICE	GreenFlux
7	Michel Bayings	Project Manager	GreenFlux
8	Hans de Boer*	CEO	GreenFlux

Table 3: Experts informants from the Norwegian setting Lyse/Smart Innovation Norway

9	Trond Thorbjørnsen	Business developer	Lyse
10	Dieter Hirdes	Project manager	Smart IN
11	Birger Clementsen	Project participant	Lyse

4 Technology domestication and end user experience

The following chapter is comprised of two parts. The first part presents findings and analysis from the investigation into end use of home chargers in Norway. The second part is a presentation of findings and analysis of expert interview data gathered from the Netherlands and complemented by three interviews with Norwegian INVADE project experts. This data serves to provide expert descriptions about the situation for smart charging in the Netherlands but, in combination with the Norwegian interview data, the report provides a more holistic perspective on smart charging development. The juxtaposition of these two cases provides grounds for comparing the two national contexts, as well as the socio-technical imaginaries of experts with the experience of real end users.

4.1 Charging routines in everyday life

As underscored in section 1.1, EV charging in Norway is for the most part done at home and with a privately owned charger. All of the pilot users reported that they would mainly charge their car at home, using the Lyse charger. At the time of the interviews, this charger was still not fully implemented into the INVADE platform and did not function as a smart charger. Still, we found that some of the pilot users would delay the charging when they plugged in the car, either via an app or by providing input manually in the car on parking, in order to schedule charging for the afternoon and night. This would time the charge to be complete in the morning, and ensure a pre-heated car, both for sake of comfort and battery life. Three main practices for home charging was found:

- The last one to use the car plugs in the charger for the day, usually in the afternoon.
- The use of car manufacturer provided app or manual direct input (i.e. in the car itself) to set a start time for charging at a time of low demand, regardless of when it was plugged in.
- Use of car manufacturer provided app or manual direct input to set a time for end of charging in order to have a heated car in the morning, regardless of when it was plugged in.

In short, and what makes this report useful to gauge experiences with smart charging, is the fact that users would themselves introduce a level of smartness to their charging, either via an app or by manipulating the settings in the car itself. This indicates that even though the charger was not smart at the time of the study, end user charging habits

already involved to some extent the practice of avoiding charging at peak hours, as this was considered “unnecessary”.

Considering it somewhat of a hassle to plug the car in every time it was parked, charging was mainly taken care of during the night. One informant explained that “*charging is tedious when the weather is wet and cold*”, as it takes time to plug the charger in and one would rather want to get inside. For any errand during the day, the battery would usually have enough charge anyway, so charging before night time was not necessary. One exception was in the case of one informant working nights who needed to charge in the afternoon or during the day. This would also vary according to battery capacity, where larger batteries usually demanded charging only a couple of times a week.

In some cases, the informants reported they did not have or use an app for setting the charging time. However, most of the cars (except the Ionic) had functionality inside the car for setting the charge times manually. It was not uncommon for users to report they would seldom work these settings manually as it was considered to be too much of a hassle. As long as the car was ready in the morning, they would simply let the charge commence from the time it was plugged in. Many pointed out that this was healthy for the battery as it kept it heated during cold winter nights. As these interviews were done in the winter time, this is reflective of the fact that many use some kind of heating implement to preheat their vehicles, whether they are EVs or not.

When discussing the possibility of charging elsewhere than home, all respondents reported they were aware of the possibility, if somewhat disinterested in doing it. Users mentioned having considered charging at shopping malls, but almost never used this kind of public charging. Again, the practice of charging away from the home was seen as involving too much hassle due to the fact that the power output for what was usually a short park was insignificant and would, in their experience, not charge the battery considerably. One informant reported they enjoyed public charging during a time they lacked charging possibilities at home. A few of the informants reported that they had in fact used shopping mall charging facilities at times when it was difficult to find parking spaces there. In these cases, they plugged the cable in to “*make it look like they were charging*”, even though they had no interest in it beyond using the parking space. Public charging was however reported to be important when going on longer trips, and a

prominent “half-way” stop between the city and a popular holiday destination in the mountains was mentioned by several of the informants.

None of our informants lived particularly far from work, typically less than a half hour drive. Consequently, most reported not using available charging infrastructures at work. One reason given for not using these was the fact that they had colleagues that drove their EVs to work from much longer distances and were considered to be more dependent on them. Also, it was reported, that due to the often-limited number of chargers available, those who wanted to use a charger would need to arrive earlier than others. The chance of any of these chargers being available at a normal arrival time was reported as nonexistent.

4.1.1 The socio-technical habits of EV driving

Most of the households in the pilots had two cars, one EV and one petrol or diesel car. The EV was usually the car that was used most of the time, thus acting as the “number one car” (see table 1). On the other hand, the fossil car was there in order to take care of extensive mobility demands, i.e. when the need arose for going on longer trips such as to a cabin in the mountains. In these instances, users would report this was due to the space constraints of the EV since it often was considerably smaller than the conventional vehicle it could not accommodate the whole family, their luggage, or for that matter, a ski-box or a trailer. In this way it was the purpose of the trip that would determine which car would be used, in some cases leaving the EV at home for longer periods.

For the rest of the time the EV was preferred due to ease of use and cost efficiency. In addition to this, many users reported the EV was superior in terms of comfort and being quieter, more maneuverable and agile, and less imposing in traffic. Many users stated that the quick acceleration that the EV was capable of exploiting the smaller gaps in traffic, although this would not be economical in terms of battery capacity - information about which is available to them due to the commonality of highly informative and graphic displays in these cars.

In-vehicle displays are prominent in EVs, and these are different from and were reported as being more informative than the ones found in conventional cars. Users often stated that this had an impact on driving habits, at least when the EV was new and new driving

habits would form. Information about charge state and rate of discharge is presented in real time while driving, and users reported perusing this information to a great extent. They did so in order to learn about their existing driving patterns, as well as to create new driving habits considered more suitable for driving an EV. One informant would talk about the practice of “*coasting*”, whereby he would keep the car in a state of minimal consumption and using the terrain to allow for the car to charge as much as possible. Another informant stated that “*The display of the car shows the battery consumption and you learn by looking at it that you can save power by driving smart*”. Yet another pointed out that it is “*exciting to drive when you see the consumption and it also is a sort of sport to save the electricity*”.

4.1.2 Family life and resource competence

Among our pilot participants we also found different types of what the literature on users of smart energy technology often refers to as the *resource man* (Strengers 2013:34), defined as an ultimate super user consuming energy in a manner that is rational according to principals of efficiency and economy, and which smart energy technology is ultimately inscribed with by design. It should be noted that the character is a stereotype useful here for analytic endeavors, and although described as a man and usually found in the real world as a man, is a label that may also fit certain women. It is thereby further useful for discussing aspects of gender in relation to smart energy technology such as smart charging.

We further divide this stereotype of the resource man into *the playful man* and *the practical man*. The practical man is showcased in our data as the ones that install smart home applications for specific purposes, exemplified by here in one of the interviews: “*I have installed a smart thermostat because I want to stabilize the bathroom floor [...] installing smart home because it is smart not cool*”. Another example on the practical man is he who has volunteered for participation in the pilot because the smart charger is fire safe and reduces charging time: “*I had just bought an electric car and was of the opinion that if you have an electric car you should have a charger in the house and not charge on a regular outlet*”. The practical approach appreciates that the charging box from Lyse is easy to use, and a good bargain as it was almost half the price. Many of the respondents were eager to join the Lyse pilot because of the simple fact that it was a good offer on an otherwise quite expensive piece of hardware.

The main drivers motivating of the playful man however, was *not* to invest in tools or technology for the smart home in order to save money or being practical, but simply because they are interested in mixing and matching and playing with their building and various technical solutions. Motivation and joy are found simply in setting up a smart home: *“I like to control the thing myself”, “I think is fun to optimize things”* and *“I think the technology and project (like this Invade pilot) is exciting”*. The barriers for the playful man is constituted by technology that he cannot play with, evidenced by expressions like: *“I don’t pay for it if I cannot play with it”, “It is when you knock yourself out and try things and do things that you find interesting solutions”* and *“I do not like technological solutions that are locked to one system (brand)”*.

The playful man enjoys exploring the newest kinds of technology and will for instance not wait until the Norwegian release of for instance an Alexa but orders it immediately from the US over the Internet and speaks to it in English (as one must). Part of what makes a technologically playful man is technological skill, often gained through a professional setting, or simply as hobby. They are frustrated by lock-ins, bundling, any kind of proprietary gadget or app, and other hindrances to their DIY aspirations of mixing and matching solutions to achieve what they consider optimal conditions. They enjoy the pure aspect of technical interoperability and making a system that autonomously operates in harmony with the routine of everyday life in the household. Such achievement often requires technical competence and adherence to highly rational principles of efficiency, and thus, not unlike an engineer, the playful man is a type of resource man.

As has been observed in previous studies of resource man type practices in households and everyday life, the aspect of family and gender can be seen as a part of this, often setting some limits or constraining the playfulness, if not acting as a de facto litmus test for the successfulness of certain technological configurations. When partners and children complain or behave in disruptive ways, it becomes evident that solutions are not simply seamlessly working in the background but capable of causing problems instead. The “wife acceptance factor” was evident in some of the interviews, as exemplified by the following quotes implicating some of the negotiation work going on in the household over these issues: *“I won’t sit on the toilet in the dark just because he like the smart light”, “I just need to know that it works”* and *“He is much more technical, so I just do what I’m told”*. However, as can be seen below, WAF is not always contingent on ease of use (as

is the underlying assumption in many evaluations of WAF), as wives, as resource men, can consider technology optimizing or practical concerns more important.

The decision to introduce smart solutions in the home, including the Lyse charger, was usually² a decision made by the playful man but on the condition set by the other household members that it “would work”. This is reflective of the fact that many families still operate with traditional gender roles. When the man wants to install a smart solution, the wife is usually more concerned about interruptions or conflicts with the regular house duties and habits (Skjølsvold et al 2017, Jørgensen, 2015). Arguably this will have some impact on the survivability of “smart” technical gadgetry in the household, as some of these improvised user testing conditions can be quite strict.

Sometimes, the consequences of the smart and technical endeavors of the playful man was providing flexibility through load shifting. However, this is seldom seen as the driver for behavioral or practice changes in these cases. Rather, the fun of exploring technology and making smart solutions work was typical driving forces. This is indicative of the fact that such solutions in fact seldom work out of the box and needs someone that can implement them in a way that makes sense in the given setting. Even if they do work according to design intentions, end users will find something that is not quite in alignment with local demands, and the playful man will start tinkering.

Furthermore, our interviews showed that aesthetics was important, and many informants (across both genders) pointed out that design can be equally or even more important than the prospect of “smartness”. The Lyse charging box was typically not complemented on having a nice design, as one respondent stated, *“it is not exactly a decoration when it is big and white”*. One of the women pointed out that *“it is big compared to his [the husband’s BMW] i3. If I had known that BMW had a box, this charging box would never had ended up in our house”*.

² Our data presents one instance in which it was a woman.

4.1.3 End user understanding of the flexibility of the grid

In Norway, in most cases the cost of this electricity for consumers is considered low, even though it has increased somewhat in the last year. Respondents were aware, but not appalled by the latest cost increases. The pilot users were also for the most part aware that prices in the future would reflect more the actual cost of grid use and power consumption. They had an idea that their network tariff could become a higher portion of their bill in the future, and that it would become possible to affect it to some degree by changing consumption behavior. However, until then, the economic incentive to shift electricity use was not experienced as pressing. Even so, we have been able to summarize some elements that make it possible for end users to become increasingly familiarized with the grid and grid issues, or what we call *grid sensitivity*.

With regards to the INVADE project and its goals, most users were aware and could understand that it had something to do with the state of the grid, and that load shifting would be beneficial from the point of view of capacity. One man compared the grid to the water: *“If everyone in the neighborhood is watering the lawn at the same time, the water pressure will be lower”*, and another was happy with the fact that *“I save the electricity grid by charging at night instead of when I come home”*. In this way, most all of our end-user respondents could be characterized as grid sensitive, meaning that they are capable of understanding grid issues somewhat from a system perspective and acknowledge end user flexibility as a way of mitigating constraints and saving money for the greater good of society.

We can however, not know whether this sensitivity was already there before they became part of the pilot project. Reportedly, the emails and information they had been provided about the project from Lyse upon being enrolled did make them more aware of the grid and the need for flexibility. Another motivation for starting to consider end use flexibility as increasingly necessary was reported by one of the informants who was living in an area that often suffered blackouts. This of course is a major cause of increasing end user awareness about power infrastructure, unusual as it is in Norway. The informant reported they had had issues often *“in the last 4 months, there has been power outages very often, almost 3-4 times a week”*.

Losing power in this way makes the taken-for-grantedness of the grid prominent and the need for some kind of solution to this problem, for instance customer flexibility, becomes easier to imagine and accept. Still a clear picture of who benefited from the aggregation and availability of this customer flexibility was in high demand: *“It is not my job to be concerned for the local grid, it is Lyse because it will be a big cost to build up the grid”*, and *“[flexibility is] smart for Lyse but not for me. They will increase prices in the daytime and move the discount to the night which I find appalling”* and, finally: *“Lyse wants control in a way so they can turn up the prices when they want”*. Again, these concerns may or may not have been there prior to this study, but the issue may still feel important to end users. In the first instance end users were concerned about whether providing flexibility would benefit society, and by extension, themselves in the long run, but they realized this would be difficult to measure in the case of individual end users. Another risk they seemed willing to live with in the face of what they could observe to be a digitalization of the grid, was the handling of personal data, and all informants had a high level of confidence in Lyse to handle it in a safe and proper way.

By and large, the “health” of the national transmission grid is not a concern at the top of the list for the average Norwegian (Throndsen and Ryghaug 2015). Making an effort to make aggregated consumption more flexible becomes realistic for end users when something brings the energy system, most of the time highly backgrounded in a routinized, everyday life, to the fore – like for instance a black out. Thus, it should be noted that something as dramatic as daily grid break downs is not the only thing that helps foreground grid issues, and we observed that this topic could be constructively debated for instance in apartment complexes and housing cooperatives in the question of EV charging. As chargers in these cases are installed behind the meter of a building’s common area, it affects inhabitants and they have to work out details and arguments, learning about grid issues along the way (Skjølsvold et al. 2017). In the continuation of this learning process, users may become increasingly grid sensitive, and this opens up for grasping the concept of flexibility in a meaningful way.

We also discussed the prospect of load curtailing with the pilot users, and how much control over their own consumption they considered feasible to relinquish to a flexibility operator or DSO in return for instance a rebate on their electricity bill. Barring some initial skepticism, many would, after some thought, consider that the water heater and eventually also the EV charger could be subjected to load curtailment, but only in case

they could opt-out whenever they deemed necessary. Asking one end user to expand on their thoughts about submitting to curtailment cause them to consider how this would be defined or agreed upon with the DSO:

“No, I need to be able to overrule the primary functions of the house. [...] I would not relinquish any control- and the same goes for the car. It is more- like when you input some settings, this is OK, right. So, if you define it as giving away control... I wouldn't put it that way.” (U7)

The quote above gives insight into the negotiation process that takes place when users consider the idea of Demand-Side Management (DSM). Initially, the idea of having any control over household electricity consumption taken away seems out of the question. However once the question of how to define how control over certain types of consumption is allocated, end users realize it is potentially acceptable to subject some consumption to automatic load curtailment. A negotiation concerning the parameters within which demand response can be acceptable takes place. It is a necessary first step for end users in order to identify which parts of their consumption is available for demand response, and also serves to establish the good conscience in which they can give it away to a third party. Emphasis for users is placed on having control when they need it as being within parameters. Like another informant said: *«as long as it does not reduce comfort, I think. If it's not warm when you get up, or if there isn't any warm water...»* it would be unacceptable.

Informants with children and teenagers living at home, with all the activity and time constraints that poses, were more skeptical toward relinquishing control. They reported they could not fathom how they could provide flexibility in addition to their already hectic life, as accomplishing tasks such as bathing of children, laundry, and other household chores all needed to be done during a few hours in the afternoon time. Social structures like school, work, nursery, and the organization of free time remain obstacles to generating flexibility for the families that participated. This indicates the ability to be flexible may change with phases in life.

4.1.4 The economic rationale of the end user

The main motivation for many people enrolling in this project seemed to be an economic rationale, since it was a very good offer on a home charger. In the outset, all respondents were already in the market for a home charger, mostly due to reasons of fire safety and the convenience of a faster charge. The offer was in much higher demand than is

reflected in the population of the demo, evidenced by the fact that Lyse had to close the registration page after just a half hour. The information about fire and proper charging have been a hot topic in debates in the media, and the Norwegian EV association have responded to this with a lot of information concerning charging. But there is also an economic rationale concerning more directly the cost of mobility in terms of operating a car, and not just the charging. This economic rationale also came up when we were talking about the motivation for buying an EV.

In the Stavanger pilot, but also elsewhere in the country, there is a heated and still ongoing debate about toll roads as a means of financing infrastructure. Given the benefits of escaping this cost for EV drivers and the relative high cost of traversing toll roads with a fossil car, this is an important driving factor for EV sales. For people working outside the city center, informants said they could have to pay NOK 200, or about €20 for each passing on the toll road. In converting to an EV, these people would save a lot of money. However, in the case they have to drive significant distances between home and work, they would be dependent on a charging infrastructure at their work place. In our data, this dependence would cause some EV drivers to come in to work at very early times in order to secure a charging spot for their car. In general, most of the economical motivation for buying an EV is that it is toll free, has low maintenance, is exempt from VAT, and, since they are in such high demand, do not lose their value as fast as conventional cars. Some, however, stated that the motivation was not to freely drive on toll roads, but that the low fuel cost was more important: *“electricity price vs gasoline price, that what’s the biggest for me at least”*, and another said: *“we have saved a lot with having electric car versus filling it with diesel”*.

4.2 Expert perspectives on EV end use and smart charging

In the following section, we will move on to the data from our expert interviews and shift the focus from Norway to the Netherlands. The experts we interviewed were all of the opinion that end users are someone who do not want too much to do with the technology itself. The end user prefers to have solutions that are simple, but with a feeling that they can control it, and as such this resonates with our findings from the Lyse pilot. Additionally, users are imagined as having an interest in saving money and making everyday life easier. Even so, we have found perhaps more evidence in the Norwegian pilot about technology interest than is present in the expectations of experts, but it can

be argued that this is due to an experiment effect causing pilot users to be more interested in technology than the general population.

As such, the case of the Dutch smart charging pilot is exemplary, as end users here did not know that they were part of a pilot project, were not able to easily identify any charger as being smarter than the conventional ones, nor were they easily able to realize they were sometimes subjected to load curtailment if they plugged into one of the chargers participating in the pilot. Thus, this presents a very different case than that of the Norwegian one but is indicative of what is the norm when it comes to charging practices in the country. However, it may be noted that if the end users had the smart charger at home as in the Norwegian case, the experts interviewed here would maybe see the end users in a different light. Further limiting the analysis somewhat is the fact that chargers participating in this specific Dutch pilot were spread across the country, and only simulated as contained within a neighborhood. The charging behavior experienced through these chargers are thus only an approximation of that of a real neighborhood. The following will summarize the most central perspectives held by the experts concerning the grid, EV use and smart charging.

4.2.1 Make it simple!

Some of our experts and developers were also users of EVs and charging equipment and would draw from their own experience when emphasizing the importance of user friendliness.

“You learn from being a user that if you like them [the solutions] you develop or not, because from a user perspective I want it to be easy, I don’t want anything too complicated.” (Int 5, Stefan)

In the mind of a designer or developer, the user when they start using a solution, decide almost at once if they like it or not. EV charging should be without any hassle because it is a part of their everyday life when you drive an EV, and people do not want to struggle with charging practices that are difficult to introduce into everyday life. The technology just needs to work when they need it:

“[Users providing flexibility] wouldn’t work people are pretty lazy yes, at least Dutch people, they don’t want the hassle.” (Int3, Arjan.)

Experts did not, from experience, consider people as concerned with electricity or power use, or that they have ambitions to become more flexible consumers. Once again dealing

with the issue of whether the user should be actively engaged in the process of flexibility aggregation, experts are generally not of the idea that end user would do this unless they find it interesting. Like one informant pointed out:

“If it is a goal to have regular energy use in the house, then the consumption in the house needs to be automatic.” (Int 10, Deiter).

Energy use in the house is something that we take for granted and we more or less expect that we can have light in our lamps and heat in our homes, and that this goes without saying. If the ambitions is to have customers take an active role toward the infrastructure of energy, it is not the energy that is the selling point, rather it will come in the shape of products that are smart in a way that makes life easier and as a side-effect provides flexibility to the grid. Like another expert points out:

“I talked to EDP, an energy company from Portugal, they said their customers do not want energy, they want light, and that way of thinking is what I always remembered. It didn’t happen because it’s quite complex, but energy companies said maybe we should not sell energy, but sell light, we start selling lamps instead of energy, and the thinking, the concept of that, I think is the right way to do it. Then you think about a user and that’s the same with flexibility, that’s the same as smart charging, no one wants smart charging, I want charging and done in a nice way.” (Int7, Michel).

In order to provide the customers with a means to charge their EVs, an infrastructure must be in place. Providing an infrastructure for charging that is convenient and easy to use is the most important step, but it also needs to make sure the charging does not cause a breakdown of the wider grid infrastructure. This work needs to happen in the background:

“If we do it properly, they should almost take it for granted, the intelligence behind it. You don’t want to know about, if you step into an elevator you go up, you don’t want to know how it technically works, you want to go up. And we make it possible that you go up. End users in principle, well, they don’t care, nor should they care. We have to provide the solutions in the background to make it possible. And I don’t think if you step into an airplane you really want to know how the aerodynamics work in detail. You are sure the company making that airplane has solved that for you.” (Int 8, Hans)

In the Netherlands case, experts were generally quite concerned about the users' need for a simplified technology. For the most part they need only to know that their EV is charging and ready for use at a designated time. This way of conceptualizing public smart charging as something that runs in the background is part of a vision of the smart city where the energy is floating silently around without people neither being or needing to be aware of it. In this case, securing the cooperation of end users is not necessary for smartness to happen. However, one aspect of end use and their conscious participation in smart charging was the end users need for a feeling of control. In a worst case smart charging scenario, an end user could plug in her EV only for it to be placed at the bottom of a long queue, resulting in the charge state not reaching a satisfactory level before the designated departure time. As the user would say in this case, then what? In the words of one of our experts: *"then they will never go to that charger again"* (Int 4, Marisca). This brings us to the idea of control.

4.2.2 The feeling of control

As we saw in section 4.1.4, when it comes to DSM, end users need to feel they have a level of control over smart charging infrastructure in order to be sure they will not be deprioritized when they need it the most. This can in many cases appear as coming into conflict with the expert's desire to make the smart charging as easy to handle as possible. This is a conundrum that our experts were well aware of. Finding different solutions or a good balance to it was considered a crucial aspect of a well-functioning smart charging infrastructure. When charging smart the speed at which the car charges can sometimes vary and become slower than usual, potentially putting an important end user asset, predictability, at risk. Like Stan points out:

"For myself I always say, the most important to me is predictability, so if you can tell me beforehand that I will be charging slow that is not even the problem, at least I can take into account, where it is difficult and most painful if its unpredictable, if I'm connecting and I have no idea how fast or even if I will be able to charge." (int 2, Stan)

On one hand, predictability is important for letting the end user know what to expect. However, and on the other hand, public charging in the Netherlands is by default highly unpredictable. With street chargers, users are not always able know what they get, so end users are by default open for the possibility of sometimes having to endure slow charging. In the case of smart charging, this is where the overrule button, available for instance on a charging app, comes in, and could make end users feel in control:

“We even have experienced here where one or two of the charge stations, they needed to have a button to overrule, and that was on the risk for the charge operator, [...] but in practice, not many people use the overrule button. It’s the same in GreenFlux, if you have an app in GreenFlux, you can do it, but [...] it is still the effort to open your mobile phone, to activate it, and even if it is 10-15 seconds, you only do that if you really need it.” (Int7, Michel)

Evidently, and from the experience of our experts, the control that is sometimes provided and considered vital for users, is not *really* needed as it is very rarely used. But it still needs to be provided, because, as in the Norwegian case of end users being reluctant to DSM unless they can have some say about it, we see that the cognitive effect of having some control over the flexible charging makes end users more open to the whole idea.

*“Mostly the app is only a one button app but if they really need to be charged as fast as possible that they press a button “charge me now” and that will happen. So we have minimum interface so they can see that they are charged and that it is going well and they can influence the priority level of charging and that’s all they do and we know in practice that they hardly use such apps but they like it, to have it available, and feeling good they have some control that, they keep some control. So basically, we give them the **feeling** of control.” (Int 8, Hans)*

The experts assume from prior experience that people will not really use the app for overruling smart charging, thus even though it in practice is not very often needed by users it was important for providing a real feeling of control:

“People all said it was very important to them to be able to override it, but in the end almost no one used it, it was used twice I think in that entire year of dozens of people participating.” (Int 2, Stan)

On the other side, the end user interviews in section 4.1 showed that some users actively used the app that came with the car to schedule charging, motivated by having a heated car in the morning.

4.2.3 What happens when smart charging is backgrounded?

As we have seen, there are some differences in the way smart charging gets practiced when we compare our two cases, however we see that rather than the causes for this being cultural, the differences are mainly due to practical and material differences. The Norwegian demonstration studied here was dedicated to implementing smart charging infrastructure at the homes of end users. The other demonstration studied here, that of

ElaadNL and GreenFlux, was quite different, mainly owing to the fact that most people in the Netherlands do not own a driveway, and thus have their charging routine relegated to nearby public chargers on street level. We asked one expert who the people using smart chargers in the Netherlands are today. The answer was:

“At the moment, not too many people, but it could be anyone. So, if you have an EV and you want to charge somewhere, you might come across smart charging without knowing it, although it’s not so general in the public domain, so smart is done behind the meters.” (Int 6, Jefta)

Parking at the street level outside their home can be considering as charging “at home” (some respondents mentioned a 70/30 distribution in favor of street parking in Holland). This means they are public as opposed to being owned by the users, who need some kind of customer relation to a charge point operator in order to use them. This of course also means that in Norway, charging consumption is for the most part behind the meter and a part of already existing, conventional household consumption. Since the chargers in the Netherlands are on the street, charging consumption is kept separate from the energy use of households.

As mentioned in the above, the chargers that were participating in the project were all spread across the entire country, and only simulated as belonging to a neighborhood area with a fixed connection cap (~700 kW). Furthermore, users in this case were not aware that the charger they were using were incorporated in a test project and that they were charging smart on behalf of a simulated neighborhood. Indeed, they had no way of knowing, since for a regular charge point user there was no immediate way to distinguish between a smart charger and a conventional one:

“If you go to a random charger, there is no way of knowing what you’re going to pay for in transaction, [...] there is no information whatsoever, so if you want to know the charge rate you have to go to the website of the charge point operator. You don’t always know who the operator is, so what website are you going to go to? If it’s not on the charger you’re lost, and they don’t want to put prices on the chargers because they might change” (Int 6, Jefta)

Because the situation in the Netherlands is that these public chargers usually do not provide any information about charge rates or prices by default, subjecting unwitting charge point users to some load curtailment for the sake of the experiment at random times was unproblematic:

“In theory, the users could know from the stickers on the charging station that says this is a smart charging station for more information you can look at our website and we explain it on our website [...]. Of course, there is always tiny issues during the operation phase when people will call in and question like: is this charger slower than it used to be? [...] Few in between, maybe 5-6 calls we’ve had” (Int 2, Stan)

In a few cases, extraordinarily astute charge point users had become aware that something was going on, probably by paying attention to charge rate via their car app, which in some cases may notify the user if charging ceases or changes. Some of these had given the charge point operators a call about this issue, reportedly more out of curiosity than anything else. In short, end users of charge points in the Netherlands had come to expect a certain variability, and that smart charging could easily be cloaked within this expected variability:

“What we decided was to have a range between 13 amps as a minimum and 20 amps as the top of the charging speed they can get. And we got to those limits by: 20 amps are the most that our charging stations can offer usually, and a nominal value would be 16 amps, you can expect it to charge. [...] If you have a two-socket charging station usually they have a grid connection of 25 amps, so when two cars are connected, they get 12,5 each. And that’s how we got to the 13 amps. [It] is the same difference as if you are the only person at a dual socket station or if there is someone else plugging in. We determined this is the variability for the user that should be taken into account” (Int 2, Stan)

In sum, we see that backgrounded smart charging in the Netherlands works exceptionally well. Since the already opaque nature of the chargers, keeping state of charge, price, and other details concerning the service provided through these chargers mostly hidden, the added uncertainty of possible curtailment due to smart charging went mostly unnoticed by users. However, there is another, more general reason for why the smart charging went unnoticed:

“There is a lot of idle time, when this [points at graph] is the connection time, only 25% of total connection time is used for charging, so there is a lot of room. So, by the end of the day, I’m plugging the car to go to work or to go home, they don’t really notice what has been going on in this time in between [...] because of the idle time of 75%. So, in 75% of the time it’s doing nothing, it can also solve its own problems so to speak” (Int 3, Arjan)

Referencing a common situation where an EV is parked and plugged into the charger for around six hours, in a conventional charging scenario, i.e. without smart charging, the

car is “just sitting there” for 75% of the time, leaving “a lot of room” in each individual charge profile for maneuvering a smart charging schedule without users noticing. This last point is true in any charging situation, not just when considering public chargers, and it points to the fact that experience from the demonstration pilot tells us that in many cases it may be possible to implement smart charging and securing large volumes of flexible EV charging without the need for user’s active participation or behavior change. As we could also see from the above, having users expect some variability can be as valuable as ascertaining a certain active behavior change.

4.2.4 Ways of thinking about flexibility

In light of these interviews and the comparison with the Norwegian case, it is possible to say that experience from the INVADE project has potential to give partial answer to the question of degree and necessity of user involvement in flexibility operation and smart energy technology deployment in general. The evidence shows that even as it is possible to secure some engaged cooperation from users like in the Norwegian pilot, it is also possible to submit electricity consumption for car charging to demand-side management in a largely unilateral fashion without causing “hassle” for end users. The case of public chargers in the Netherlands, a situation comparable to that in similar countries, is especially clear cut when it comes to this potential, because it is a framework of public service provision in which users have few options. In this way it makes not only a strong case, but also an early case with precedence setting potential, in which flexibility may be defined as something that is “up for grabs”. Like one expert iterated, “it is a place you can control”:

“This charging of EV is really secondary energy use, you have primary important residential use and then you have energy use that we can curtail in some way, that’s what all of this project is about, and I think it’s a very important question to figure out when is it fair to limit the charging speed, why is charging less important than watching TV or laundry, why is it always charging that we are looking at? I think it is because it’s an area you can control” (Int 2, Stan):

Early conceptualizations of the flexibility market usually designate end users an important role, not just in a participatory fashion, but also as a contractual decision maker that may “allow” for their flexibility potential to be exploited. A prerequisite in this way of thinking about flexibility is that for flexibility to be exploited, the customer must willingly enter some form of contract in which flexibility is defined as a commodity they own and would like to place on a market of competing buyers. Like we saw in the Norwegian case,

securing engaged participation from end users into relinquishing consumption to Demand Side Management requires a negotiation on part of the user.

However, as we can see from the experience made in the Dutch pilot, cases exist in which flexibility may be considered an ownerless leftover, or flexibility as residue, which can be put to use for the greater good of the system or to cover for some other shortcoming in the organization of the grid. Thus, it is possible to distinguish between different ways of putting this excess resource to use, providing at least two important perspectives into the debate on how to conceptualize flexibility. The first one is when flexibility is not needed to solve grid congestion, but may be used to get rid of excess renewable energy in periods of low demand:

“The other thing is, where the DSO see a potential in using electric vehicle batteries is to mitigate the peaks of the sun and the wind, especially sun, and I think in that perspective, I mean, you can do two things: you can cut off the solar panels, so the people that make use of those solar panels have less money, or you can use electric vehicles batteries to provide those solar panel users. You have room to sell more solar power, in that case I think the people owning the Electric vehicles should be compensated, you are helping someone else sell more solar power, then you should be also compensated for it. And if you are maybe you can do voluntarily so I want to lend you my battery so you can do those kinds of things.” (Int 1, Fedja)

This means that aggregate EV users may not only be subject to charging curtailment in order to stave off excess demand, but in order to make their batteries available as depositories for excess *supply* of electricity in the grid, that otherwise may have incurred the generator a fee in order to dispatch it. It is *“a way to deal with the variability and unpredictability of renewable sources” (Int 2, Stan)*, thereby increasing the usability of these resources in the grid as a whole.

Another way of putting this is as described from the supply perspective: *“I have the supply perspective, who wants to have the consumer to consume as much as possible of electricity and when supply is also high, that is also smart charging from another perspective” (Int 3, Arjan)*. This perspective is rooted in the need for balancing efforts in the grid as a consequence of unexpected deviations from scheduled consumption. As electricity is traded and bought on the market to deliver to customers for the following

day by energy companies, a Balance Responsible Party (BRP) will sometimes need to ameliorate unexpected increases or decreases in demand:

“If you [the BRP] see that, oh we have been off our targets for a bit, then you can either purchase pretty expensive power on the spot market or you can tell a few chargers to charge a bit slower or faster, that’s where that business model is, so they are able to save money from purchasing expensive power from their miscalculations and they’re using the charging flexibility in the charging stations to compensate for it.” (Int 2, Stan)

This summarizes two ways in which flexibility can be considered useful – either as a means to get rid of excess renewable energy or as a way of ameliorating miscalculations in expected demand. However, it should be mentioned in reality it is less clear cut as in some cases these two applications can contribute to solving the same problem.

Furthermore, there are still other cases where the concept of flexibility as residue may not apply as easily, even though technically the situation may be comparable. One such situation is exemplified by the Norwegian case, defined as it is by home ownership, owned parking, and owned charging infrastructure placed behind the meter. This configuration results in EV charging consumption getting added to the already existing, conventional household consumption. This provides variation in scenarios on which arguments can be made for expecting end users to more or less willingly provide their flexibility:

“My first thought is obviously the most important thing that we have to do here is make sure that we can sure to get rid of the fossil fuels and keep our energy grid working, that should be the goal, the high level goal, which means we should expect people to provide with any flexibility they have in order to achieve this societal goal, [...] that’s one of the ways I’m thinking about this.” (Int 2, Stan)

And this way of thinking about it is one that will bring people on board, However, there is also a possibility that flexibility may be exploited purely by profit motives.:

“I am a little concerned about this turning into a money optimizing game for the BRPs, it should be optimize based on real societal problems I think, to solve the problems for society, not to make a few companies richer.” (Int 2, Stan)

In summary, there are different ways of conceptualizing flexibility, and they vary according to the circumstances in which it has been aggregated (public vs. private), but also to what purpose it is going to be put to use (societal good vs. cost of balancing). This poses a question yet to be answered as renewable shares increase, smart energy technology gets further deployed, and aggregated flexibility increases in value – causing methods and technologies to more effectively (and more invasively) appropriate it. The final and currently most unexplored issue then is how to assign value to this unclaimed resource:

“You pay a price to charge the car with kilowatt hours and then you sell it back to the grid so you get some money in return, and you charge again and what do you do with the profit if you charge cheaply and sell at a high price and then charge cheaply again? Of course, there's some benefit, but is it all for the EV driver or is it partly for the person who made the algorithm to do it? [...] you will probably need some extra incentive because also you're causing battery degradation and, at least that's what people think, that is not so good for the battery.” (Int 4, Marisca)

Charging and discharging the batteries is something that theoretically causes degradation, and this may become an issue when these batteries are the property of end users. Even if this from a technical point of view is a negligible point, for instance compared to the charge and discharge of driving itself, it is “what people think”. Thus, it can be expected, even if it can be more or less successfully established (as in the above) that active and engaged users are not necessary for successful flexibility operation of smart charging, they may nevertheless engage on the topic of compensation. The many ways in which flexibility comes about and makes itself useful may have important bearing on how the issue of compensation for users should be worked out. It is not unlikely that smart charging will have a precedence setting effect on the formation of the entire flexibility market since it is here these issues first will have to be worked out.

5 Discussion

The charging habits of our end user informants were deeply connected to their everyday routines, and for the most of them the routine was to charge when the last one in the family was arriving at home. According to domestication theory there are three central aspects of appropriation of technology, namely the practical, cognitive, and symbolic. In the practical domain there are issues concerning charging and battery capacity, as cars are becoming outfitted with better and better battery capacity. A consequence of this is that people are not concerned about charging anywhere but home except when they intend to drive for longer distances.

5.1 Socio-technical imaginaries and the affordance of end users

The active role of users in meeting technology evidences that they are not simply passive or rational. Akrich (1992) use the concept of script to explain how the affordance of an artifact is written into artefacts as scripts that attempt to manage the user trajectory. The way the object is finally used is then contingent on not only the composition of the script, but how the script is read and interpreted by the user, which again is dependent on their script reading competence. The concept of script can explain how different individuals in the same situation can come to hate or love the same piece of technology (Tjora, 2009, p. 207), which is because the script may afford (or not afford) different use trajectories for those individuals. This leads us, on the basis of our findings, to *a typology of four different socio-technical imaginaries of end users that indicate different degrees of customer engagement and each propose different barriers to implementation of new technology (see figure 1)*. This shows that individual interest and the potential use context has an impact on how technology is domesticated. Technological interest is a factor that can vary in regard to the context in which the technology is implemented, and, in that context how necessary it feels to use it. For example, this can be when an individual appropriates an EV charger because charging from a regular outlet is prohibited where they live. The context provides demands of necessity, and this can come from material conditions surrounding the home, but also internal and external laws or norms that influence the domestication of technology.

In today's society the contextually necessary varies all the time, as in the case for instance of a smart phone, which we can use to pay the bus ticket with an app or control

smart lighting that changes color according to the rhythm of the music that is playing. It is in the intersection of contextual necessity and technological interest we end up seeing distinctly different end users. Reflecting what we often observed in the case of our end users, the names of the categories in this typology carry the name of men, inspired by Strengers (2013:37) concept of the **resource man**. The resource man is a man “not always because he is always directly identified as one, but because he is cast in the image of the male-dominated industries of engineering, economics and computer science, and because visions of him exclude most household labor.” Combining the two concepts of technological interest (high to low) and contextual necessity (that means the level from high to low need for the new type of technology) provides us with the following typology.

Figure 2: Types of end users

Practical man: This user is easy to like from the point of view of the technology designer, because he already has a lot of smart technology in place and is interested in experiencing new solutions – including those that are on the drawing board. These kinds of users are not representative of the rest of the population, but they are easy to involve in the innovation phase and development of technological solutions, such as pilot projects. They exhibit high technological interest and view it as necessary to seamlessly manage energy consumption so that it stays within economical parameters. This user falls within the early adopter-phase of Roger’s innovation adoption curve (1995). The main motivation for the resource man is to get a technological solution that works, so he can rest in an assurance that household energy consumption is as efficient as possible.

Playful man: The main drivers motivating this particular kind of user was *not* to invest in tools or technology for the smart home in order to save money or being practical, but simply because they are interested in mixing and matching and playing with the building and various technical solutions. The motivation and joy here are found just in the setting up of an own smart home. The playful man can, like the resource man, be valuable assets in a technology development setting, but are also demanding users. They do not like bundled, proprietary and incompatible tech, and are not interested if they cannot open the hood and tinker inside.

Involuntarily resource man: The technology is often designed for resource men and in some indirect way the technologically uninterested man is forced to get to know this technology because the use contexts demands that the technology is implemented. Technology is a part of how gender is negotiated in relation to the occupation, symbols, identities and structure (Lohan and Faulkner, 2004), and in some case the man can be faced with the attitude that it is expected that he likes to learn new technology. In this sense, it becomes evident that all men are not resource men but may still adapt and behave according to technological design because he is compelled by expectations in his surroundings.

Tech aversive man: This man is not interested in technology and does not care that he is expected to. The tech repulsive man does not find any joy of getting to know new technological solution and works toward using the minimum amount of technology that he needs to use to survive in his everyday life. This is a type of user that fits well with situations where technology just works in the back ground. However, here it must be noted that many technologies considered as “just working” has been placed in that mode by a playful or resource oriented end user. Tech repulsed users will not engage in set and forget-type of technologies, as even these types of efforts are not worth it in terms of cost-benefit.

If we understand the end-users in the use contexts and their technology interest, we get a more nuanced pictures of who they are and how they react to for instance different performance indicators like price regulation.

5.2 The context of flexible end use

Through our analyses of the end use of EVs and smart charging we have identified four ideal types of smart charging practice, corresponding to four kinds of imagined users, that have been enrolled in the Invade project. These practices give different potential for what we can call *grid sensitivity* (Skjølsvold, Henriksen and Ryghaug, forthcoming), according to how active or passive the users are intended to be in relation to the technology. Grid sensitivity means people's ability to be aware of the grid and develop an electricity consciousness, turning invisible electricity consumption into a visible part of everyday practices. Grid sensitivity among end users can have an impact on their decision making and willingness to invest and partake in solutions like the ones provided by the INVADE platform.

In our data it was possible for people to attain either higher or lower grid sensitivity across a spectrum of awareness. We find that the more potential for grid sensitivity is found in nurturing a user base that is active and engaged, and that where technology “that just work” is in place, less potential for affecting grid sensitivity is present. For instance, sociotechnical configurations of end users with private homes and their own driveway, with a private charger that was connected to the household electricity have a high potential. Conversely, sociotechnical configurations consisting of users living in apartment flats without designated parking lots available, and who use public parking with associated public charging infrastructure that does not provide information about charge state or status, have a low potential for developing grid sensitivity among its users. This does not say anything about the actual grid sensitivity of these users, which we do not know, only that the configuration itself affords more or less in the way of engaging users with grid issues. It also does not suggest that these latter solutions do not work in a satisfactory way compared to the home charger variant, because the fact that they “just work” is their main characteristic.

In the model below, grid sensitivity potential is extrapolated from the vertical arrow. The horizontal arrow relates to the level of collective decision-making processes in installing smart charging or charging infrastructure. When it is low, few people are involved in the decision, like in the instance of an office building or a board in a company, or in those situations where only one household member makes the decision. When it is high, the decision to invest in technology is taken collectively, involving a higher number of people

in the decision process. The latter is more robust in terms of producing grid sensitivity but may end up in rejecting the technology. The former produces conditions that to a greater extent ensure the technology is implemented, but does not leave much room for social learning.

Figure 3 An overview of the different contexts in which learning about the grid happens

By using this level of *collective decision* making and potential for *grid sensitivity* among people as two dimensions we get four different *ideal types*³ of end users' involvement with smart charging. With ideal type we mean that this is a theoretical approach to understanding the different end users and what context they are a part of.

Public smart charging: Whether to build and maintain a charging infrastructure in a city or municipality is an issue that is heavily influenced by the political system in any given area. Public smart charging infrastructure is a cost that is paid by the local governing body (i.e. a municipality or county), and so the decision process surrounding the question to build one is highly collective. The grid sensitivity potential incurred by using the chargers is however not very imposing, and the design is not dependent on involving end

³ According to Nasu 2005:129 "Weber characterized the nature and the function of the ideal type as being "like a utopia which has been arrived at by imaginative accentuation (gedankliche Steigerung) of certain elements of reality." (Weber, 1904: 190)"

users to a great degree. Similarly, in the Netherlands, the DSOs have been implementing charging stations, and this is at a lower level of decision making, even though the DSOs act on behalf of greater society. In any case, end users are not engaged, and the design does not require them to. This leads to low potential of grid sensitivity, however it is a case where the technology really does “just work”.

Company smart charging: The potential for grid sensitivity in this category is low and the level of decision making is also low. This situation occurs typically in companies where they have installed smart charging for their own or their employees’ EVs, usually adjacent to their premises or in a garage that they themselves own and can make independent decisions about. Users of this infrastructure do not need to be engaged to a large degree, and this is a case again of technology that “just works”. It has a slightly higher grid sensitivity potential, as an employee may identify with their place of work, and also with the strategy to implement e-mobility measures. However, the user need not worry about anything other than plugging in and does not have to concern themselves about for instance flexibility behavior, as opposed to in the case of the home charger.

Smart charging at home: Here, the potential for grid sensitivity is high and the collective decision making is low. This means it is often just one of the household members recommending the implementation of a charging unit to the others, arguing that smart charging can be a good solution as it increases convenience and fire safety. In our data the smartness was an argument as it could save money, but at the time of the study the role of this was hypothetical because it had yet to be fully implemented. Many of the grid sensitive in this case are typical resource men, who are interested in implementing smart charging since it is a sensible thing to do.

Joint property smart charging: In this case, which we find in for instance cooperative housing situations, there is a high potential for grid sensitivity as well as a high level of collective decision making. Here, not just one person or a board concerned with a shared parking garage partake in the deliberation on the issue of smart charging, but all the residents who own a stake in for instance a co-ownership, joint property or housing cooperative. The decision to build smart charging infrastructure in these cases needs to be subjected to a democratically sound process where, for the project to move forward, the majority of the tenants have to vote in favor of the investment. Inhabitants have

different opinions about e-mobility as well as different income situations that influence how they may view this added expense to the common bill (since the charging infrastructure is often installed behind the meter of the coop). The process takes time, and in some cases the decisions is not always in favor of early adopters. However, the high level of collective decision-making may conducive to grid sensitivity, as the level of involvement of decision makers requires the tenants to vote. Of course, it is possible in these cases to abstain, but then they will need to live with the collective decision.

This empirical model of the INVADE end users shows us how the different contexts gives us some ability to pre-interpret how to address the end users. For any given pilot or e-mobility project it can be useful to problematize the level of involvement for end users. In many cases they do not need to know if they are charging smart or not, and that it can be more in accordance with the goals of the project to have a solution “that just work”. However, when technology just runs in the background, the potential for building up grid sensitivity is probably quite low. These differences in potential for grid sensitivity must be considered when deciding when and where the new energy market end users should be given an important role for delivering flexibility or not.

6 Conclusions

The delays in completing and implementing the INVADE platform did have an impact on what kind of end users experience was available for analysis. Some pilot users were simply not exposed to the INVADE platform since it had not been implemented. In the rare case (i.e. Badenova) that users had been exposed to a configuration of solutions that provided user experience with INVADE-like functionality, unfortunately the group of users was too small and too exhausted to be exposed to additional empirical enquiry. As these are private citizens that need to go about their lives, this does put limits on how intensely they can be exposed to us as objects of study. To mitigate this, the report instead focused on end use experience with EVs and smart charging. Charging habits are country specific and contingent on different everyday practices and factors such as building regulation and the amount of public and private places available.

Another finding in this report is that the use of concept as *Grid sensitivity* shows that the end users with EV are not locked into just one type of flexibility understanding but have an interest in understanding flexibility as useful for the DSO and the BRP, even if this interest may be motivated in different ways. The different ways this interest is motivated has been categorized and defined in this report. It provides a framework within which developers can understand this interest and recognize how to employ it to further business development and innovation of the INVADE platform. This includes being sensitive to the playful nature of some end-users and involve them in the design project at an early stage. Conversely, it gives advice on how to approach users that are less playful, more practically oriented, or simply technology averse.

The empirical finding from our interviews with end users and experts can be summed up in these findings:

- The charging habits are closely connected to everyday life. In the Netherlands people charge when coming to work in the morning and in Norway they charge mostly at night. The peak of EV charging is dependent on national cultures related to material qualities such as dwelling structure and practices. Thus, whether users are renting or owning their dwelling, and if they have private or public parking lots or not, is decisive of charging habits.
- As we saw in our findings, the difference between private and public charging habits has huge implications on how smart charging can be implemented. In the

private setting users need to be engaged in the technology to a larger degree. In the public setting it is much more feasible to simply let technology work in the background.

- Invade experts imagine end user as tech averse, but the Invade pilot users are playful and practical when involved in the project. This is a resource that can be exploited by involving the playful and practical end users in the innovation process. The playfulness can be targeted as a resource where the end users get access to play with the technology.
- It is mostly men signing up for the pilot studies. This means that the recruitment strategies need to be changed to get the women on board.
- It may be possible to implement smart charging and securing large volumes of flexible EV charging without the need for user's active participation or behavior change. As we could also see in our findings, when it comes to securing flexibility, having users expect some variability in their charge rate can be as valuable as ascertaining a certain active behavior change on their part.
- Smart charging in private homes can have a precedence setting effect on the flexibility market since it is here issues related to e.g. customer remuneration, market contracts, and privacy first will need to be worked out. This is especially valid in countries with high market penetration of EVs, but other prosumer technology like batteries and PV of course apply.
- In conventional understanding, the prediction is that the smart meter is turning the home flexible. Our results indicate that smart charging is making end users grid sensitive as it is oriented towards a practical issue.
- In this way, smart charging opens up a practical-material means of engaging with grid flexibility, and in that way directly impacts end user motivation to becoming a prosumer.

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8 Appendix

8.1 Appendix 1: Interview guide Norwegian case

This interview is a part of the INVADE WP 9 about the end user experience in this case with smart charging. We do know that the charger is not smart yet, but we hope to get some inside in your expectations to smart charging and you charging habits in the everyday life.

Motivation to be a pilot user:

You are pilot users of Lyse. What made you sign up for this pilot?

Have you been pilot users before?

Where did you hear about Lyse's pilot project?

Was everyone in the household equally interested in the project?

How long have you been a part of the pilot now?

Something that has been surprisingly positive / frustrating about being a pilot user?

How did you experience Lyse's electric car smart charger installation?

What information did you get in advance?

Did you get extra courses be added / was there enough electricity on the course?

What charging solution did you have before?

Why did you choose this solution?

What kind of opportunities do you think this will hold in the future?

In your own words, why have you installed an EV charger from Lyse? What is the goal of Lyse's project?

Electric car use in everyday life

Did you have EV from before?

How long have you had the EV?

Why EV?

Who in the family decided on a new car / electric car?

What model of electric car do you have?

Why did you choose this model?

Does everyone in the household use the car?

Have you had any previous experiences with electric cars?

What are you using the electric car for? (The electric car is the main car, For the daily commute, Local errands, Long trips, or other?)

Where do you travel with the electric car?

Why do you choose to use the electric car for this?

Do you have more cars? Which? Why, and what is it used for that does not cover the electric car?

Do you plan your trip differently when driving an electric car? (everyday, weekend, vacation)

How many hours a day between 06:00 and 24:00 is the electric car parked? Or in another way how many hours is the car on the road? (approx. hours)

EV Charging

Where and when do you usually charge the electric car? (home, work, mall, fast charging)

How often do you charge the car?

Who is responsible for charging the car?

Do the EV have a fixed parking space? What kind of charger possibility do you/the parking have?

Have you charged the EV in other places like hotels, public garages, other private houses, car parks?

What is the cost of charging an EV vs. filling gas on a conventional car?

How do you pay?

Have you changed your driving style after starting an electric car?

What kind of info do you get from the in car-dashboard?

Has it affected your driving in any way?

Do you schedule/program the car's charging hours?

Can you explain your usual patterns for doing this?

Do you or your household use the car differently during weekdays and weekends?

(More or less use? Other charging pattern? Other routines?)

What do you suppose is the annual mileage? (approx. km)

How is this mileage compared to other cars in the household?

Have you experience range anxiety?

How many hours a day between 06.00-24.00 is the car parked? (approx. hours)

Do you/youre familit have other cars? Which? Why?

APPS. (bmw, charging station app, lyse, smartly)

Which Apps do you use for the electric car?

Do you have any apps that give you an overview of energy use on the electric car?

Any apps that help you keep track of energy usage in your home?

Are there any features your apps lack? (power consumption?)

From stupid to smart charger. (Control / automation)

What meaning do you put into smart charging?

How do you understand the term power peaks? Explain.

How do you see the possibility of power companies or others taking over the control of some household appliances? (such as the charger, hot water tank etc)

What do you think if the grid company or others decide when the electric car is charging? (automatically switched off to reduce power peaks)

What processes in the home would you like to automate?

What are the biggest challenges with this kind of smart management?

What are the possibilities?

Are you worried about what your consumption / charge data can be used for?

Do you want to control the energy manually or automatically?

How much control could you give away to get cheaper electricity?

Smart technology and energy use in everyday life

What do you think of when you hear the term "smart technology"?

Do you have any smart technological solutions in your house?

Have they changed any routines in the home that affect power consumption?

Have you experienced that some smart solutions have changed your energy habits?

Are you thinking about energy use? Become more proven with the electric car charger?

What do you think of when we say consumer flexibility?

Have you become more flexible?

Do you have solar cells on the roof? Is there anything that could be relevant?

If so, what would be the motivation?

Would you like to store electricity (for home use, for others) on your electric car?

Could you let your neighbour have electricity from your electric car?

Have you become more interested in related technology such as smart home technology, solar cells and heat pumps?

The future of the car/the transition from car to EV or car free society.

What kind of role have the EV in the future?

What do you think the transition to more EV will entail? Way do you think so?

What role do you think the electric car has in creating electricity grid flexibility?

Closing question.

How many lives in the household?

What is the age to the people in the household?

What is your profession?

What education do you have?

What are your leisure activities?

Final reflections.

What do you think about the future? (Energy and climate.)

Having your electric car made you more interested in participating in energy and climate change work? (energy citizenship)

8.2 Appendix 2: Interview guide for INVADE D9.2. Expert users the Netherlands case.

This interview is a part of the INVADE WP 9 about the end user experience in the demo projects. In the Netherlands case, the end users are also expert users and part of the development team. Topics we will cover end user experience with the INVADE platform, but also topics on technology development and project context. The questions are for the most part non-technical in nature, open ended, and designed to elicit descriptions of current conditions in the pilot. To this end, we are interested in stories about important events, thoughts and insights, and decision processes that have led up to this point. Interviews are recorded and will be described for further use in research.

Background Information.

Can you tell us what is your professional background? What is your role in Elaand/GreenFlux?

What kind of responsibilities/tasks do you have towards the INVADE pilot?

Why (how) did your company join the INVADE project?

The end user.

Who are the typical end users for the smart Charging?

What do you believe is the main motivation for the end users to charge smart? What has been your motivation?

Smart charging, load shifting and user flexibility

Who do you believe will profit on smart solutions?

Will other end users have more benefited than others?

Will anyone have a problem with delivering the flexibility? And who do you think? And what consequences will that have for end users?

What is smart charging, how does it work and what are the motives for implementing smart charging? Explain as you would to a 12 year old.

How active do you think the end user will need to be? (what will you as an end user need to do manually and what is done automatically in the background?)

Is it this the same as V2G? How will you define that?

How important is load shifting?

Is load shifting it in demand? By whom?

As an end user, how much control over your own consumption are you willing to relinquish to the system? Who will assume this control instead?

How do end users provide flexibility? By changing behavior patterns or by implementing technology that aggregates it automatically?

What are the possibilities in this technology?

What, in your opinion, is the best way to motivate consumer flexibility?

Penalty / reward in price?

What role does price and information play in motivation?

Is it one more important than the other?

Pilot user and their EV.

How do you balance the task of being both user and developer?

When did you get your first EV?

Why did you choose an EV?

Who in the family was the driving force for getting an EV?

Which model EV do you have and

why did you choose this model?

Does everyone in the household use the car?

Is EV ownership common where you live?

Do you plan your trips differently when driving an electric car? (everyday, weekend, holiday)

What do you use the car for? (It is the main car, for the daily commute, local errands, longer journeys, other?)

EV Charging in daily life

Where and when do you usually charge the electric car? (home, work, mall, fast charging)

How often do you charge the car?

Who is responsible for charging the car?

Do the EV have a fixed parking space? What kind of charger possibility do you/the parking have?

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What kind of info do you get from the in car-dashboard? Has it affected your driving in any way?

Do you schedule/program the car's charging hours? Can you explain your usual patterns for doing this?

Do you or your household use the car differently during weekdays and weekends?

(More or less use? Other charging pattern? Other routines?)

What do you suppose is the annual mileage? (approx. km)

How many hours a day between 06.00-24.00 is the car parked? (approx. hours)

Do you/youre familit have other cars? Which? Why?

Apps and other functionality

Which apps do you use in connection with the electric car? What information and service do they give?

Are there any features you lack the apps? (power consumption?)

The INVADE Project.

Can you quickly describe the INVADE pilot that your are working on? What is the goal of the pilot? What kind of technology is involved in this project?

What is the ideal outcome? How close are you to this ideal so far?

How do you identify and involve users/customers in your work? How to learn from them?

What is the biggest challenge in developing the INVADE platform, the technology or the end users? What is the challenges related to upscaling the platform?

Reflection about the process in the end.

Based on your experience, what is the most challenging part of such a process in general and in Invade?

What would you say are the benefits of doing innovation in EU projects such as INVADE?

What do you want to say are the challenges?